

Understanding the influence of leaf litter on the water balance composition of blue-green infrastructure

Prabhat Joshi^{1,2,*}, Juan Naves³, José Anta³, Max Maurer^{1,2} & João P. Leitão²

¹Institute of Environmental Engineering (IfU), ETH Zürich, Stefano-Franscini-Platz 5, 8093 Zurich, Switzerland

²Department of Urban Water Management (SWW), Eawag, Überlandstrasse 133, 8600 Dübendorf, Switzerland

³Universidad de Coruña, Water and Environmental Engineering Research Team (GEAMA), Center for Technological Innovation in Construction and Civil Engineering (CITEEC), Campus de Elviña, 15071 A Coruña, Spain

*Corresponding author email: prabhat.joshi@eawag.ch

Highlights

- We compared the hydrological performance of a green roof for “reference” and “leaf litter” scenarios.
- Leaf litter (2 kg m⁻²) increased the overland flow volume and sped up its concentration time.
- Initial soil moisture content and leaf litter influenced the green roof’s water balance components.

Introduction

From centralised, end-of-pipe-based “grey” infrastructure, urban stormwater strategies have increasingly embraced decentralised, blue-green infrastructure (BGI) such as bioretention cells, porous pavements, or green roofs. BGI offer various hydrological, ecological, aesthetic, and societal benefits as part of their multifunctional design, due to which urban water engineers and planners are increasingly proposing their implementation, with or without pipe-based drainage systems in the mix. From an urban hydrological perspective, BGI reduce runoff volume by storing rainwater on-site, which is then evapotranspired or exfiltrated into surrounding soils (water *retention*) (Stovin *et al.*, 2013). BGI also temporarily store water to lower the peak flow rate, slow runoff concentration time, or control the outflow rate (water *detention*) (Stovin *et al.*, 2017).

Many studies have focussed on BGI planning and designing requirements and strategies. However, like any other urban water infrastructure, BGI also require regular maintenance and upkeep to preserve their hydrological performance, an aspect which is overlooked and understudied in published literature (Blecken *et al.*, 2017). We hypothesise that an unmaintained BGI will have reduced hydrological benefits, which need to be considered when planning and designing BGI for cities for their long-term performance.

Against this context, we present the first results of an experimental study to establish the maintenance requirements of BGI. The study’s general objective was to *understand the impacts of poor maintenance on BGI’s hydrological performance*. Here, we present the effects of leaf litter on a green roof, assuming that the expected effects are similar in other BGI as well. The specific objectives — concerning leaf litter accumulation — were to:

1. Quantify the changes in the water detention characteristics
2. Quantify the changes in the runoff (overland flow) and underdrain flow volume and characteristics
3. Quantify the changes in the water balance components

Methodology

Overview

We experimented at CITEEC¹ in the University of Coruña (UDC), Spain, which is equipped with an indoor rainfall generator (Naves *et al.*, 2020), to supply a fixed rainfall pattern to a green roof under different scenarios (described later). We then computed and compared the hydrological performance for each

¹ CITEEC: <https://www.udc.es/gl/citeec/hidraulica-en.html>

scenario by quantifying the water detention metrics (time to start of underdrain and overland flows) and the green roof's water balance components.

System configuration

The rainfall generator, which was initially capable of producing 30, 50, and 80 mm h⁻¹ (Naves *et al.*, 2020), was adapted to generate less intense values so as not to limit our study to extreme events. For the rainfall pattern, we used a typical, symmetrical hyetograph (13.3 mm) with intensities ranging from 17 to 56 mm h⁻¹ and for 25 minutes—long and intense enough to produce both underdrain and overland flows.

The green roof, housed in a wooden box and covering a 3.84 m² area (Fig. 1), comprised a vegetation layer (*Sedum sp.*) atop a 6 cm deep, green roof-suitable substrate layer of pozzolans, expanded arlite, and pumice stones. The substrate layer rested on top of a storage layer containing HDPE trays², into the bottom of which a pipe was placed for the water to release (underdrain flow). The surface runoff was channelled into an outlet point in the box (overland flow). The overland and the underdrain flows were measured using tipping buckets connected to a data logger, while the soil moisture level was measured using a TEROS 12³ capacitance sensor. The spatial distribution and intensity of rainfall were calibrated by collecting rainwater in uniformly distributed vessels on the green roof and weighing the collected water amount for a fixed amount of rainfall depth and duration. The soil moisture sensor was calibrated by using an oven-dried soil sample, which was first wetted and then allowed to dry all the while recording their soil moisture content. The recorded soil moisture values were compared against the weight of the sample to obtain a calibration curve.

Figure 1. Overview of the green roof housed in a wooden box with tipping buckets to measure underdrain and overland flows.

Green roof scenarios

For the scenarios, we first ran the rainfall pattern into the green roof, which served as the baseline or the “Reference” scenario (Fig. 2(a)). Then, we added 8 kg (~2 kg m⁻²) of wet broad-type leaves (*Platanus x hispanica*), spread evenly across the roof (Fig. 2(b)) to achieve a dense leaf litter scenario, based on Sato *et al.* (2004).

Figure 2. Green roof scenarios: (a) reference scenario with no leaf litter, and (b) green roof covered with 8 kg (~2 kg m⁻²) of leaves

² HYDROPACK® green roof trays, Vegetal i.D.®: <https://www.vegetalid.com/solutions/green-roofs/the-all-in-one-system-hydropack.html>

³ TEROS-12, METER group: <https://www.metergroup.com/en/meter-environment/products/teros-12-soil-moisture-sensor>

Results and discussion

Leaf litter showed an increase in overland flow volume and led to a decrease in the concentration time

Fig. 3 shows the time series of the underdrain flow (Fig. 3(a)) and the overland flow (Fig. 3(b)) from the green roof for the preliminary tests of the two scenarios described above. The underdrain flow for both scenarios started roughly 10 minutes after the start of the rainfall. As for the overland flow, the roof with leaf litter had overland flow almost as soon as the rainfall began, in contrast to the reference scenario, for which it began approximately 11 minutes after the rainfall started. The cumulative sums of the underdrain flow (Fig. 3(c)) and the overland flow (Fig. 3(d)) showed a decrease in underdrain total volume (0.5 mm) for the leaf litter scenario and an increase in the overland flow volume (1.1 mm).

Figure 3. Time series and cumulative sum of (a, c) underdrain flow and (b, d) overland flow for the “reference” and “leaf litter” (2 kg m⁻²) scenarios

This meant that excessive leaf coverage likely sealed the surface, which may have caused a considerable portion of the rainfall water to be intercepted and flow laterally very quickly. The broad-type leaves have a high relative water content to maximum water storage capacity ratio (> 1), meaning that extra rainfall water was most likely to be intercepted at the upper part of the litter layer in its surface pits rather than percolating downwards in the soil layer (Sato *et al.*, 2004). The quickening of overland flow and the increase in its magnitude may have been compounded since the leaf litter coverage was high (≥ 2 kg m⁻²) and the rainfall intense (> 30 mm h⁻¹) (Sato *et al.*, 2004). This means that BGI, designed to slow the concentration time, are potentially susceptible to poor performance when excessive litter accumulates on their surface.

Leaf litter seems to influence the green roof’s water balance components

As the leaf litter increased the overland flow volume, we found that other components of the green roof’s water balance might have been affected as well (Fig. 4). In comparison with the “reference” scenario, the amount of underdrain flow and water retained in the soil was lower for the “leaf litter” scenario whereas the amount of water intercepted was higher.

It is worth noting that the “reference” and “leaf litter” scenarios had different initial soil moisture conditions (1.6 mm and 2.7 mm, respectively). The soil had a higher initial water content for the “leaf litter”

Figure 4. The green roof's water balance components after 150 min of rainfall at which point the underdrain and overland flows have effectively ceased

scenario, so it required a smaller amount of additional water to initiate the underdrain flow. This can also explain why the amount of water retained in the soil in the “litter scenario” was smaller – the soil moisture retention characteristics did not change between the two scenarios. In addition, and as a consequence of the increased overland flow in the “leaf litter” scenario, less water could reach the soil layer, contributing to a smaller underdrain *total* volume when compared to the “reference” scenario.

Conclusions and future work

We presented the results of a preliminary experiment to understand the hydrological performance of poorly maintained BGI by adding leaf litter to a green roof and comparing the generated overland and underdrain flows with those generated by a reference green roof. The preliminary results showed that:

1. Leaf litter caused the overland flow to start soon after the rainfall began and the total overland flow volume to increase.
2. Leaf litter reduced water infiltration into the soil, leading to lower underdrain flow volume.
3. Leaf litter seems to have influenced the water balance composition, notwithstanding the experiment's different initial soil moisture conditions.

More experiments are currently being conducted to quantify the changes in the water balance composition with *incremental* leaf litter against the reference system. In the future planned experiments, similar initial soil moisture conditions will be maintained to minimise their influence on the final water balance composition. The rainfall pattern will also be varied to observe the hydrological response of an unmaintained BGI to various rainfall conditions. These experiments will provide insights into understanding BGI dynamics and helping to emphasise that their maintenance is crucial to ensure their optimal hydrological performance.

Acknowledgements

This work was partially funded by the EU under the Horizon 2020 program within a contract for Integrating Activities for Starting Communities (Co-UDlabs project. GA No.101008626). The corresponding author's doctoral study is being funded by the Engineering for Development (E4D) scholarship, ETH Zürich.

References

- Blecken, G. T., Hunt III, W. F., Al-Rubaei, A. M., Viklander, M., and Lord, W. G. (2017). Stormwater control measure (SCM) maintenance considerations to ensure designed functionality. *Urban Water Journal*, 14(3), 278-290. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1573062X.2015.1111913>
- Naves, J., Anta, J., Suárez, J., and Puertas, J. (2020). Development and calibration of a new dripper-based rainfall simulator for large-scale sediment wash-off studies. *Water*, 12(1), 152. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w12010152>
- Sato, Y., Kumagai, T. O., Kume, A., Otsuki, K., and Ogawa, S. (2004). Experimental analysis of moisture dynamics of litter layers—the effects of rainfall conditions and leaf shapes. *Hydrological Processes*, 18(16), 3007-3018. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.5746>
- Stovin, V., Poë, S., and Berretta, C. (2013). A modelling study of long term green roof retention performance. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 131, 206-215. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2013.09.026>
- Stovin, V., Vesuviano, G., and De-Ville, S. (2017). Defining green roof detention performance. *Urban Water Journal*, 14(6), 574-588. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1573062X.2015.1049279>